

The land-ocean Arctic carbon cycle

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Abstract

Anthropogenic climate warming is amplified in the Arctic, impacting the Arctic carbon (C) cycle and its role in regulating climate and global biogeochemical cycles. In this Review, we provide a quantitative and comprehensive overview of the present-day Arctic carbon cycle across the land-ocean continuum. Terrestrial soil stocks total 877 ± 16 Pg C, with upper marine sediments containing 82 ± 35 Pg. Overall, the integrated Arctic system is a carbon sink, driven by oceanic uptake of CO_2 (127 ± 36 Tg C yr^{-1}) and organic carbon burial in shelf sea sediments (112 ± 41 Tg C yr^{-1}). Terrestrial systems, including inland waters and disturbance, are a net source of CH_4 (38 (21, 53) Tg yr^{-1}) and CO_2 (12 (-606, 661) Tg C yr^{-1}). The Arctic carbon sink will likely weaken under continued warming, owing to factors such as increased coastal erosion, outgassing of riverine organic carbon, and enhanced nearshore carbon turnover lowering shelf sediment burial. Arctic greening and increases in terrestrial carbon sinks will be substantially offset by increases in soil respiration, disturbance from extreme events, and enhanced emissions from inland waters. Future research should prioritize enhanced coverage of small catchments and nearshore regions, and inclusion of non-linear responses in biogeochemical models.

Website Summary

Anthropogenic warming is perturbing the Arctic carbon cycle. This Review provides an overview of contemporary carbon stocks and fluxes across terrestrial, aquatic and oceanic components of the integrated Arctic system.

Key points

- Amplified warming in the Arctic impacts all components of its biosphere, hydrosphere, and cryosphere. These physical changes affect carbon cycling within and between short-term and long-term terrestrial and marine reservoirs.
- Large databases, research syntheses, and time series have improved quantification of terrestrial and marine stocks of carbon, as well as lateral fluxes (fluvial and erosional), and vertical fluxes (emission and burial).
- Carbon cycling is expected to intensify under continued anthropogenic warming and carbon source-sink dynamics are expected to shift towards a weakened carbon sink function of the integrated Arctic system (land and ocean combined).
- Increasing occurrence of extreme events and non-linear changes pose a challenge to the accuracy of future projections of carbon-climate interactions.
- Future research should prioritize interdisciplinary collaboration, consortia and programs to work holistically across system boundaries and scales.

Introduction

Since the 1980s, the Arctic has been warming nearly four times faster than the mean global rate¹, with far-reaching consequences for all Arctic system components and their carbon (C) stocks and cycling. There is large variability in the rate and direction of ongoing change across the Arctic, owing to simultaneous perturbations of multiple processes that lead to spatially divergent responses². Nevertheless, it is apparent that anthropogenic climate change is already transforming the Arctic and its C cycle, and it is becoming increasingly difficult to assess the direction and magnitude of change within the context of what has previously been considered normal³.

The Arctic is important in regulating the global climate system^{4,5} and global biogeochemical cycles⁶, with circum-Arctic soils hosting about twice as much C as the atmosphere⁷. Much of this C is in perennially frozen permafrost soils and largely shielded from active participation in global C cycling. When permafrost thaws, these C stocks are exposed to degradation, lateral transport and potential release to the atmosphere

as greenhouse gases⁸⁻¹⁰. Arctic soils are drained by fluvial systems that together deliver more than 10% of global discharge into the Arctic Ocean, which is a relatively enclosed ocean basin. This ocean is shallow (approximately 50% of the ocean consists of <200m shelf seas¹¹) and small in volume (only 1% of the global ocean¹²), which makes the Arctic Ocean and its shelf seas highly connected with and influenced by its terrestrial hinterland (Fig. 1a). Therefore, the Arctic is a highly integrated system, with recipient shelf sea basins being strongly hydrologically coupled with their respective terrestrial watersheds. Land-ocean organic C (OC) fluxes can increase ocean acidification¹³⁻¹⁵ and impact marine ecosystems, with long-term sequestration in marine sediments being an important geological C sink¹⁶. Thus, changes in the connectivity of C stocks, fluxes and cycling across the integrated Arctic system can impact global C cycling.

Anthropogenic climate warming^{1,4} and the increasing occurrence of extreme events, such as heat waves and boreal or tundra fires^{17,18}(Fig. 1b), are perturbing the Arctic C cycle. Melting sea ice¹⁹ (Fig. 1c) and ice sheets²⁰, increasing terrestrial discharge²¹, warming and thawing of frozen ground²², and coastline collapse²³ all directly or indirectly impact the Arctic C cycle, by enhancing physical and biological degradation, altering hydrological flow paths, and changing sediment dynamics across landscapes²⁴. A number of research initiatives and databases have improved the quantification of C reservoirs and fluxes between different components of the Arctic and improved process understanding of the impact of climate change on C cycling over the land-ocean continuum (such as the [Circum-Arctic Sediment Carbon DatabasE \(CASCADE\)](#)²⁵, the [pan-ARctic CAtchment DatabasE \(ARCADE\)](#)²⁶, the [REgional Carbon Cycle Assessment and Processes 2 \(RECCAP2\)](#)²⁷, the [Arctic Great Rivers Observatory \(ArcticGRO\)](#)², the [Northern Circumpolar Soil Carbon Database \(NCSCD\)](#)²⁸, the [Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost \(GTN-P\)](#)²⁹ and the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme of the Arctic Council³⁰). However, most comprehensive overviews of the Arctic C cycle are over 15-20 years old^{31,32} and precede the last decade of amplified Arctic warming. Thus, to assess responses to ongoing environmental change, an updated overview of the current state of the Arctic C cycle is needed.

In this Review, we synthesize quantitative data on all C cycle components along the Arctic land-ocean continuum, from the catchment soils to the marine sediments. We use the broadest definition of the Arctic Ocean and its drainage basins (Fig. 1a) and we also include Hudson Bay, Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Baffin Bay, Greenland Sea, Norwegian Sea, and Bering Sea. C stocks and fluxes in the pan-Arctic domain include terrestrial and marine (sediment and water column) stocks, lateral fluxes from rivers and coastal erosion, as well as vertical fluxes on land (terrestrial and aquatic) and in the ocean (emission to or uptake from the atmosphere and accumulation in marine sediments). For each of these components we detail the most pressing uncertainties and data gaps. We conclude by discussing the implications of anthropogenic climate change on the Arctic C cycle, and suggest that future research should focus on underrepresented areas, such as fjords and small catchments, and the impact of non-linear processes, including extreme events.

Carbon stocks

The Arctic is a heterogeneous system consisting of varied landscapes and ecosystems shaped by different depositional histories and climates. Within this system, OC resides in long- and short-term reservoirs, or is in transit. In this section, the three main OC reservoirs, that is the terrestrial sediment, marine sediment and marine water column stocks, are discussed. Note that, unless stated otherwise, only the upper 300 cm of permafrost soils and the upper 200 cm of non-permafrost soils within the northern circumpolar drainage basin (Fig. 1a) are considered here, owing to data availability.

Terrestrial stocks

The northern circumpolar drainage basin is home to large soil OC (SOC) stocks that have accumulated over many millennia, forming an important component of the global carbon cycle⁷. Terrestrial SOC stocks in the

upper soil of permafrost and non-permafrost regions total 877 ± 16 Pg C (Fig. 2a; Table 1, see Supplementary Note 1, Supplementary Table 1), equivalent to 26% of the total global SOC stock of ~ 3350 Pg C (ref.³³). However, SOC is not homogeneously distributed across different landscapes, soil types, or soil profiles. For instance, permafrost soils store 540 ± 10 Pg C (62% of the total SOC stock in the northern circumpolar drainage basin), with 174 ± 3 Pg C (20%) stored in the seasonally frozen active layer and about 292 ± 7 Pg C (19%) stored in unfrozen and seasonally frozen soils in non-permafrost regions (Table 1). Deep (>3 -50m) terrestrial OC stocks can also be substantial, for example Pleistocene-aged ice-rich permafrost holds 297-436 Pg C (ref.³⁴).

How SOC stocks are distributed within the landscape and soil profile largely determines their vulnerability to mobilization, degradation and subsequent release as greenhouse gases. Biotic and abiotic decomposition of SOC is governed by a complex interplay between climate, soil properties (including mineral protection of OC³⁵), hydrologic regime, and landscape dynamics³⁶. Thus, SOC stocks are not all equally vulnerable to thaw, bioavailable to microbial greenhouse gas production, or accessible for hydrological transport (Fig. 2b).

Large spatial heterogeneities in SOC distribution make quantifying the vulnerability and accessibility of SOC stocks difficult. Vertical soil column data suggest that ~ 21 Pg C is stored in the upper 30cm of permafrost, directly below the active layer. Deepening of the active layer, which has progressed at a rate of 0.11 ± 0.35 cm yr⁻¹ between 2003 and 2020 in the northern permafrost region³⁷, exposes this SOC to degradation and mobilization. However, around 20% of the permafrost region is underlain by excess ground ice, rendering the landscape vulnerable also to collapse upon ground ice melt³⁸, known as thermokarst. These ice-rich deposits have relatively high SOC content³⁸ and could provide a similar climate feedback as the remaining permafrost area where there is limited ground ice³⁹. Although thermokarst events and the resulting mobilization of deeper SOC are relatively localized, their incidence is increasing³⁸ and they trigger substantial lateral transport (Fig. 2c, d) of SOC into aquatic ecosystems^{40,41}. However, drainage of thermokarst lakes also initiates vegetation recolonization and permafrost aggradation leading to C uptake and freeze-locking⁴². Based on the vicinity to potential drainage pathways, the total hydrologically-accessible SOC is 487 ± 8 Pg, consisting of active layer stocks (174 ± 3 Pg), upper 30cm of permafrost (21 ± 0.4 Pg), and non-permafrost soils (292 ± 7.4).

The vulnerability of these hydrologically-accessible SOC stocks (Fig. 2b) to mobilization depends on the drainage and degradation potential of their respective terrain classes. Based on their slope and relative height above the nearest drainage point (HAND⁴³; Supplementary Note 1, Supplementary Table 2) (Fig. 2b), terrain classes conceptually represent vicinity to the water table and potential drainage, ranging from waterlogged soils at the valley bottom (for example, peatlands/wetlands), to transition (ecotone) soils moving away from rivers and lakes, followed by sloped soils, and lastly plateaus⁴³.

Terrain classes indicate processes most likely to mobilize SOC. Of all hydrologically-accessible SOC (487 ± 8 Pg), $\sim 41\%$ is waterlogged, 19% is in the ecotone/transition class, 21% is in the hillslope class and 15% is in the plateau class (Fig. 2b; Supplementary Fig. 1). Waterlogged SOC stocks located in ice-wedge polygon terrain⁴⁴ are vulnerable to changes in lateral flux dynamics upon thaw⁴⁵. In other regions rich in ground ice, thermokarst lake formation could expose previously freeze-locked SOC stocks to methanogenic decomposition⁴⁶. SOC stocks in ecotone terrain rich in ground ice are often subject to low-energy lateral flux processes via release of dissolved organic carbon (DOC), except in higher energy regimes, such as near large rivers, where stocks are more vulnerable to lateral export as particulate organic carbon (POC). Broad hillslope and plateau classes include a range of possible hydrological outcomes. Hillslopes are high-energy environments characterized by erosion processes, such as gullying, slumping, or active-layer detachment. The dominance of mass-wasting processes under gravitational forces means that POC release dominates mobilization fluxes^{38,41}. Plateaus have the potential to be hydrologically isolated and waterlogged on shallow bedrock or when permafrost conditions are fully intact reducing hydrological connectivity,

however, if there is a thick sedimentary overburden, plateaus can become sensitive to mass wasting upon permafrost degradation, as on the Canadian Peel Plateau⁴⁷.

Although local and landscape scale processes dictating permafrost vulnerability and OC remobilization are well constrained⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰, modelling these processes at the pan-Arctic scale is not as advanced. However, substantial progress has been made since 2015 to incorporate thaw processes and lateral coupling through hydrological connectivity in ice-rich permafrost landscapes at regional scales^{45,51,52}.

Marine sediment stocks

Seafloor sediments are key receptors and sinks of exported terrestrial OC and the Arctic Ocean shelf areas receive disproportionately high fluxes of organic matter from coastal erosion and river discharge relative to other oceans⁵³. Estimates presented here are integrated over the surface sediment (0-1 cm) that most readily interacts with other biogeospheric compartments such as the overlying water, and the integrated sediment column (0-100 cm).

OC stocks in circum-Arctic shelf sediments can be estimated based on sediment OC concentrations and dry bulk density data obtained from sediment cores of the seafloor. The total OC stock in the top 1 cm for the seven Arctic Ocean shelf seas (excluding Hudson Bay, Bering Sea, Baffin Bay and Greenland/Norwegian Sea) is estimated to be 529 ± 107 Tg C (mean \pm s.d., Fig. 3a Table 1, see Supplementary Note 2). The largest portion of this OC is on the Barents Sea shelf (170 ± 43 Tg C, $\sim 32\%$), which is also the largest shelf sea by area (1790×10^3 km²), whereas the narrow Beaufort Sea shelf hosts just 17 ± 4 Tg C ($\sim 10\%$), proportionate to its much smaller area (183×10^3 km²).

Data for deeper sediments across the Arctic Ocean are sparse. Earlier estimates suggest a Holocene OC stock of 95 Pg C (excluding the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Hudson Bay, Bering Sea, Baffin Bay and Greenland/Norwegian Sea)³¹. Based on about 2000 OC observations integrated over 0 – 100cm depth, this updated estimate suggests the marine sediment OC pool is 82 ± 35 Pg C (Supplementary Note 2, Fig. 3a). However, the thickness of the Holocene layer varies greatly across and within regions. This variation in sediment thickness is due to variable sedimentation rates in space and time, which also leads to variations in OC mass accumulation rates (Fig. 3b). For example, the Holocene layer thickness varies between a few centimetres to tens of meters thick in the Russian Arctic seas⁵⁴, and from a few decimetres on the eastern shelf to tens of meters in the Mackenzie Trough in the Canadian Beaufort Sea shelf⁵⁵. Therefore, OC stocks in Arctic shelf sediments are best described by discrete depth intervals (for example 0-1 cm and 0-1 m), as a lack of information on sediment thickness prevents reliable time-integrated OC stock estimates for Arctic shelf sediments.

Marine water column stocks

Despite constituting just 1% of the global ocean volume⁵⁶, the Arctic Ocean receives approximately 11% of global river discharge^{57,58}. These high freshwater inputs subject the Arctic shelf seas to stable stratification⁵⁹ with limited vertical mixing⁶⁰, and contribute large quantities of terrestrial matter, including sediment, C and nutrients to coastal shelves and the central Arctic Ocean^{2,61,62}.

Marine water column stocks of OC are highly dynamic in space and time (Supplementary Fig. 2). Water column C concentrations in nearshore, coastal, and shelf waters are primarily governed by seasonality in ice cover^{19,63}, light conditions, and terrestrial inputs (fluvial and erosional) of C and nutrients^{48,63}. These processes regulate primary production in the ice-free season^{64,65}, under the ice in spring, as well as the remineralization of OC⁶⁵ and the export of terrestrial C to the coastal ocean. Changes in river discharge and ice melt have led to freshening of (parts of) the Arctic basins^{30,66}, which strengthens stratification, ocean acidification¹³ and affects light and nutrient availability⁵⁸.

DOC constitutes the largest OC pool in the marine water column (Fig. 3c). Based on conservative mixing ratios between DOC concentration and salinity⁶⁷, annual mean DOC stocks across the water column for the six high-Arctic shelf seas (Barents, Kara, Laptev, East Siberian, Chukchi and Beaufort Sea) are estimated at 506 ± 14 Tg (Table 1; Supplementary Note 3; Supplementary Tables 3, 4), with the NEMO-PISCES ocean general circulation and biogeochemistry model suggesting a total labile DOC pool of 172 ± 0.38 Tg across the entire Arctic shelf (Table 1). Large uncertainties originate from multiple processes, including additional sources of DOC, degradation of DOC, and sea ice meltwater mixing. By area, the Barents, Kara and Beaufort seas have the largest DOC stocks (0.11 - 0.12 Tg C per 10^3 km², Fig. 3c; Table 1), whereas by volume, the Laptev and East Siberian seas have the largest DOC stocks (1300 - 1373×10^{-6} Tg C per km³, Supplementary Fig. 2b). High volume-normalized DOC stocks in the Laptev and East Siberian seas likely result from their shallow character together with large river discharge and high coastal erosion rates. In general, salinity-derived DOC stocks are 5 to 10 times higher than those derived from the NEMO-PISCES model, as the model does not simulate refractory DOC.

Poor data availability limits estimation of circum-Arctic POC stocks. However, regional estimates for the Laptev and East Siberian Seas of 1.32 ± 0.09 Tg and 2.85 ± 0.20 Tg POC, respectively⁶⁸, consist of >50% of terrestrial POC and degrade at similar rates as water column DOC⁶⁸.

Autochthonous sources, such as marine net primary production (NPP) also contribute to marine OC stocks. Estimates of annual NPP in the Arctic Ocean vary greatly, from 241 (138, 422) Tg based on remote sensing to 691 ± 18 Tg based on NEMO-PISCES modelling (Table 1). NPP rates are dependent on terrestrial nutrient inputs from rivers and coastal erosion⁶⁵, and exhibit strong seasonality with peak rates in summer and rates nearing zero in winter (Supplementary Table 4). Simulations from the NEMO-PISCES model indicate that around one third of Arctic Ocean NPP is driven by lateral nutrient supply from rivers and erosion⁶⁵. Although estimates of annual NPP from remote sensing and NEMO-PISCES modelling differ considerably (Fig. 3d), they are within the same order of magnitude and show similar regional trends^{69,70}.

Similarly, remineralization within the water column acts as an autochthonous sink of OC. NEMO-PISCES simulations of DOC remineralization suggest that rates peak in September and continue at slow rates throughout the winter⁶⁵. However, model-derived quantitative estimates have large uncertainties owing to inadequate representation of lability of organic matter from rivers and erosion⁷¹. OC lability remains poorly constrained owing to sparse observations⁷²⁻⁷⁴, and the lack of representation of coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) and POC in NEMO-PISCES⁷¹, which might explain the relatively high rates of NPP in simulations compared to those derived from observations⁷⁵. These discrepancies in NPP could arise from the omission of explicit CDOM simulation in NEMO-PISCES increasing light availability in surface waters, potentially leading to an increase in the simulated NPP. In addition, CDOM can be mistakenly identified as chlorophyll in satellite-derived NPP estimates, resulting in overestimation of NPP.

Terrestrial soils in the northern circumpolar drainage region and marine sediments on the Arctic Ocean shelves store vast amounts of OC, making them among the largest OC pools on Earth. OC in surficial deposits is especially vulnerable to mobilization through thaw, thermokarst, and hydrological release in terrestrial environments and through resuspension, bioturbation and cross-shelf transport in shallow marine environments. Highly dynamic water column OC stocks are sourced from terrestrial DOC and marine primary production and are therefore influenced by seasonality, ice cover, and terrestrial inputs.

Lateral carbon fluxes

Fluvial transport and coastal erosion are the primary lateral transport processes transferring C from terrestrial to marine stocks. Fluxes associated with each process are highly seasonal and deliver material to the shallow Arctic shelf seas, supporting and impacting coastal and marine ecosystems.

Fluvial fluxes

The Arctic hosts about 20% of all river and stream surface area on Earth⁷⁶. These drainage networks connect terrestrial systems to the ocean and atmosphere, and facilitate biogeochemical processing and transport of terrestrial material^{49,77}. The intensifying hydrological cycle, widespread permafrost thaw, and potential changes to within-catchment and within-stream organic matter processing² will impact pan-Arctic fluvial fluxes and, thus, biogeochemical fluxes into coastal ecosystems (ref.^{65,78,79}).

The six largest Arctic rivers – the Ob', Yenisey, Lena, Kolyma, Mackenzie and Yukon – cover 10,860,000 km², equivalent to 44% of the Arctic Ocean watershed (Fig. 1). Annually, these rivers deliver 18 Tg C as DOC, 3.1 Tg C as POC, and 30 Tg C as DIC to the Arctic Ocean⁸⁰, with CO₂ fixation within the catchments supporting 44% to 59% of the DIC flux^{62,78,81} and aquatic biomass representing a substantial (39-60%) proportion of the annual POC flux⁸² (Fig. 2d). The majority of these annual fluxes are delivered during the spring freshet and summer months (for example, 80-95% of DOC⁶²). Alkalinity and DIC fluxes have increased across the Arctic since 2003 (ref.^{2,83}), owing to the exposure of deeper soils and increased weathering². Whereas pan-Arctic sediment fluxes vary regionally reflecting differences in erosion susceptibility^{41,84}, DOC fluxes have remained relatively constant since 2003 owing to the occurrence of multiple changes with divergent responses, such as increased processing of material within watersheds versus increased vegetation and litter input due to shrubification².

The remainder (ca. 56%) of the terrestrial Arctic is drained by >47,000 ocean-terminating watersheds²⁶. Mostly smaller than 1000 km², these systems account for 98% of watersheds by number but only 9% of the total northern circumpolar drainage basin. Often consisting of permafrost-dominated tundra and ice-wedge polygon terrain, these watersheds have a fundamentally different topography and climate regime than the larger basins. Whereas discharge, fluxes, and yield (flux per unit area) are well constrained and homogenous in larger basins (variability between rivers is 3-, 8-, and 3-fold for DOC, POC, and DIC yield, respectively), yield measurements for these remaining small systems are sparse (Supplementary Table 5) and highly variable (50-, 1,300- and 9-fold for DOC, POC, and DIC yield, respectively). Flux estimates rely on extrapolation over substantial basin areas (Supplementary Fig. 3, Supplementary Note 4) as observations are scarce, particularly in the Chukchi Sea, Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Hudson Bay, and Baffin Bay drainage basins. Thus, the estimated annual fluvial fluxes of 39.5 (17-90) Tg DOC, 8.21 (1.5-37) Tg POC, and 65.4 (23-102) Tg DIC (Table 2) from the northern circumpolar drainage basin come with several limitations and uncertainties, owing to their reliance on extrapolation, and lack of representation of processes such as biogeochemical effects of deltas⁸⁵ and C sorption, leaching, and flocculation processes during transport⁸⁶.

Coastal erosion

The Arctic Ocean is surrounded by approximately 407,680 km of coastline⁸⁷. Climate change is enhancing coastal erosion in the Arctic via lengthened open water periods, warmer air and sea temperatures, deeper permafrost thaw, more intense storms later in the season and rising sea-level⁸⁸. Ground ice melt in permafrost coasts further enhances their vulnerability to collapse and erosion⁸⁹. In addition, sediments, C, nutrients and contaminants from the entire soil column, not just the upper layers of soil, are vulnerable during coastal erosion. Following mobilization, material is washed into the dynamic nearshore zone^{23,90}, where C can be degraded and released to the atmosphere^{23,74}, buried in shelf sediments^{23,91-93} or transported further offshore^{23,94}.

Erosion of the Arctic shoreline has accelerated since the early 2000s relative to the latter half of the 21st century⁹⁵. However, most evidence is from specific areas of interest that collectively represent less than 10% of the length of the circum-Arctic coast, covering urbanized areas⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸ and regions of rapid change^{99,100}, economic interest¹⁰¹ or military use¹⁰². Thus, understanding of Arctic coastal erosion and associated OC

fluxes is largely limited to regional hot spots, such as Drew Point in Alaska^{100,103}, the Yukon coast in Canada⁹¹, or the Lena Delta in Russia¹⁰⁴.

Pan-Arctic estimates of OC fluxes from coastal erosion are in the range of 4.9 to 14 Tg yr⁻¹ (ref. ^{87,105}) (Table 2). However, limited observations of OC content¹⁰⁶, cliff height and ice content mean that these estimates rely on extrapolation to large stretches of coast with potentially large uncertainties, particularly as they do not distinguish between release as DOC or POC. Eroding material is likely predominantly released in the particulate form (ca. 80%) over DOC (ca. 20%)^{31,107}, but release of DOC from melting massive ground ice might also be notable¹⁰⁸.

Pan-Arctic OC-fluxes can also be estimated from remotely-sensed observations of coastal erosion rates¹⁰⁹. A remote-sensing based estimate for regions where coastline erosion rates are >2 m yr⁻¹ or >1 m yr⁻¹ (based on practical detection limits¹⁰⁹) suggests OC fluxes range between 2.03 and 2.74 Tg yr⁻¹ (ref.¹⁰⁹), respectively (Table 2; Fig. 2c; Supplementary Note 5). Uncertainties in erosion rates are of the order of 0.3 m yr⁻¹, which accounts for an SOC flux uncertainty of up to 0.25 Tg yr⁻¹. These fluxes are much lower than the 4.9-14 Tg yr⁻¹ range derived from the Arctic Coastal Dynamics (ACD) database, owing to cliff heights in the ACD database being 2-8 times higher than those applied in the remote sensing-based derivation (Table 2). However, only about one quarter of the coast is included in the remote-sensing approach as erosion rates for the remaining coastline stretches fall below the threshold of 1 m yr⁻¹. These remote sensing-based OC flux rates are therefore technically robust but only represent a fraction of the whole coast and are therefore conservative.

Observational evidence shows that coastal erosion rates and associated matter fluxes have been increasing in various places throughout the Arctic⁸⁸, and these rates and fluxes are projected to increase further until 2100 (ref.⁶³).

OC fluxes (mostly as POC) from coastal erosion into the Arctic Ocean are of the same order of magnitude as riverine POC fluxes, with fluvial DOC fluxes being an order of magnitude higher. Whereas the peak of riverine matter fluxes occurs with maximum discharge during the spring freshet (May-June), erosion is most efficient later in the season (August-September) when storm frequency is highest and thaw depth is at its maximum. This seasonal difference could lead to diverging ecosystem and climatic responses of C cycling in the Arctic Ocean.

Vertical carbon fluxes

Vertical C fluxes (that is, the emission and burial of C) occur across the entire land-ocean continuum. In this section, the C emissions from terrestrial and aquatic systems and burial in ocean sediments are discussed. Uptake is represented by negative flux values and emissions are represented by positive flux values. Terrestrial fluxes include fluxes from inland waters, unless stated otherwise.

Land-atmosphere fluxes

The net land-atmosphere C balance of the permafrost region and the entire Arctic Ocean watershed are poorly constrained but can be estimated using bottom-up and top-down approaches. Bottom-up approaches, such as data-driven upscaling based on surface flux measurements, support estimates that are integrated at regional scales, whereas top-down approaches, such as atmospheric inverse modelling based on atmospheric observations and transport modelling, support local to regional scale estimates.

Top-down estimates of land-atmosphere CO₂ fluxes for the northern circumpolar drainage basin suggest that the basin was a net sink of atmospheric CO₂ between 2016 and 2020 (ref.¹¹⁰, see Supplementary Note 6). Integrating across the terrestrial system, including emissions from inland waters, these estimates indicate

that this integrated regional sink is on the order of $-740 \pm 220 \text{ Tg CO}_2\text{-C yr}^{-1}$ (mean \pm annual mean standard deviation), equivalent to a land flux of $-0.06 \pm 0.02 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4a; Table 2, Supplementary Fig. 4a). Other top-down estimates also show that the terrestrial Arctic is a C sink over this period, ranging from -320 to $-1390 \text{ Tg C yr}^{-1}$ (ref.^{111,112})(Supplementary Fig. 4b). Another estimate based on an ensemble of four inverse models indicated that the Arctic zone was a sink of CO_2 , with total uptake of $-130 \text{ Tg C yr}^{-1}$ between 60°N and 90°N (ref.¹¹³). Differences between inversion estimates might result from differences in priors and their assumed errors, transport models, data used for assimilation, and areas and time periods analysed.

Top-down estimates show that land-atmosphere CO_2 fluxes are spatially and seasonally variable across the Arctic. Land C fluxes across the northern circumpolar drainage basin have a clear seasonal cycle, with net C uptake occurring during the warmest period (May to August) and modest C release between September and April (Supplementary Fig. 4a). In addition, sensitivity tests indicate that the annual mean sink ranges from -690 to $-820 \text{ Tg C yr}^{-1}$ between 2016 and 2020, reflecting regional differences in the annual mean land fluxes. For example, northeast Siberia and Alaska act as a small net source of C to the atmosphere with the other regions acting as a small sink. The GCP^{111,112} top-down estimates show a similar seasonal pattern in fluxes, but with spatial distributions of fluxes varying between the different models (Supplementary Fig. 4b).

By contrast, available bottom-up estimates suggest that the permafrost region of the northern circumpolar drainage basin is a weak CO_2 source. Although there are no bottom-up estimates specifically for the northern circumpolar drainage basin, mean annual bottom-up budgets for CO_2 and CH_4 for the years 2000-2020 are available²⁷ over the northern permafrost region within tundra and boreal biomes (17 million km^2)¹¹⁴, covering 78% of the northern circumpolar drainage basin as defined in Fig. 1 (see also Supplementary Fig. 5). Emissions from the northern permafrost region, including inland waters and disturbance, are estimated to be $12 \text{ Tg CO}_2\text{-C yr}^{-1}$ (95% CI range of $-606 \text{ Tg CO}_2\text{-C yr}^{-1}$, $661 \text{ Tg CO}_2\text{-C yr}^{-1}$) and $38 (21, 53) \text{ Tg CH}_4\text{-C yr}^{-1}$. These estimates account for emissions from disturbances, such as fire and abrupt permafrost thaw, and emissions from inland waters, but omit lateral transport of OC. Terrestrial bottom-up estimates omitting emissions from disturbances and inland waters (Table 2, also spatially resolved by drainage basin) sum up to be $-218 (-749, 156) \text{ Tg yr}^{-1}$ for CO_2 and $22.9 (12.2, 33.2) \text{ Tg yr}^{-1}$ for CH_4 , indicating the importance of disturbance and inland waters to vertical C fluxes in terrestrial systems.

Earlier evidence for parts of the northern circumpolar drainage basin shows that the region is an important and consistent source of CH_4 to the atmosphere¹¹⁵. Observations and regional process-based models suggest emissions of 11 Tg C yr^{-1} (uncertainty range between 0 and 22 Tg C yr^{-1} , 1990-2006) and 26 Tg C yr^{-1} (uncertainty range between 16 and 35 Tg C yr^{-1}) across the Arctic tundra region, respectively¹¹⁶. Bottom-up estimates also report a total CH_4 emission of $12.45 \text{ Tg CH}_4 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for the Arctic zone (between 60° and 90°N)¹¹³. Direct comparison of these estimates is difficult, as they cover different spatial extents, but there is general agreement on a CH_4 source on the order of $10\text{-}40 \text{ Tg CH}_4\text{-C yr}^{-1}$.

By comparison, there is a lack of agreement for CO_2 as top-down approaches indicate a CO_2 sink and bottom-up approaches indicate a source. Although all the estimates remain data-limited¹¹⁷, the uncertainty ranges of different methods overlap and there is potentially bias in sink strength in prevailing data syntheses²⁷, it is likely that the region is a net sink of CO_2 and source of CH_4 . Given the higher radiative forcing, but shorter atmospheric lifetime of CH_4 compared to CO_2 , the net radiative forcing effect from the northern circumpolar drainage basin is a weak warming on decadal timescales, but a net cooling at centennial timescales. However, the balance between CO_2 and CH_4 depends on local moisture conditions post thaw^{50,118}, and warming-induced increases in microbial activity might further intensify C mineralization, both in soils and in aquatic systems.

Inland aquatic system-atmosphere fluxes

Inland waters cover ~6% of the northern terrestrial land area¹¹⁹ and actively contribute to the global C cycle. OC is buried in lake sediments^{120,121}, but lakes, ponds, rivers, and streams also emit CO₂ and CH₄ through diffusive mechanisms at the water-air interface, ebullition (bubbles), and via plant-mediated transport¹²². CO₂ and CH₄ emissions from northern inland waters are understudied compared to those of wetlands¹²³, contributing to high C emission uncertainties.

Bottom-up estimates indicate that Arctic inland aquatic systems are a net source of CO₂ and CH₄. Emissions of CH₄ and CO₂ from inland waters estimated by bottom-up approaches are orders of magnitude higher than those of top-down approaches^{111,124}, with bottom-up estimates reported here. In the early 2000s, northern inland waters are suggested to be a source of both CO₂ (40-85 Tg C-CO₂ yr⁻¹)³² and CH₄ (15-36 Tg C-CH₄ yr⁻¹)^{122,125}. Later estimates since the early 2000s, based on improved data availability and scaling methods, suggest that regional and global aquatic emissions of CO₂ have increased^{27,126,127} but emissions of CH₄ have decreased^{27,125,128}. Across the northern circumpolar drainage basin, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions from lakes and rivers are of the order of 253 (146-361) Tg C-CO₂ yr⁻¹ (mean and 95% confidence interval) and 9.4 (4-16) Tg C-CH₄ yr⁻¹ between 2000-2020²⁷ (Fig. 4a; Table 2). Regionally, the Kara Sea (63 Tg C yr⁻¹), Laptev Sea (55 Tg C yr⁻¹), and Hudson Bay (46 Tg C yr⁻¹) drainage basins are the largest sources of inland water C emissions. Across the circumpolar north, aquatic C emissions are mostly in the form of CO₂ and are dominated by river emissions, except for the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and Hudson Bay (Fig. 4b, 4c). Normalised to drainage area, aquatic emissions of CO₂ and CH₄ are largest in the Laptev, East Siberian, Bering and Beaufort drainage basins (Fig. 4b, 4c).

Emissions from inland waters offset the terrestrial carbon sink. The net terrestrial flux is derived from combining total emissions from inland waters (summing CO₂ and CH₄ gives 262 Tg C yr⁻¹; Table 2) with terrestrial fluxes excluding those from inland waters (sum of -195 Tg C yr⁻¹; Table 2). Both rivers and lakes are net sources of CO₂ and CH₄, where rivers are largest contributors of CO₂ and lakes of CH₄. The net radiative forcing for inland waters is therefore warming on both decadal and centennial time scales. Thus, the net terrestrial flux is converted from a sink of -195 Tg C yr⁻¹ to an annual C source of 67 Tg C.

Ocean-atmosphere fluxes

The Arctic Ocean is a net sink of atmospheric CO₂. Estimates suggest that the annual CO₂ uptake of the Arctic Ocean ranges from -52 to -226 Tg C yr⁻¹ (ref.¹²⁹⁻¹³⁷). The Arctic Ocean has the largest CO₂ uptake by area of the global oceans owing to an enhanced solubility C pump (due to the progressive cooling of northward flowing subpolar waters)¹³⁵ and seasonally enhanced biological CO₂ uptake (due to the combined effects of seasonal sea ice melt on light availability and lateral fluxes of nutrients from rivers and erosion enhancing NPP)^{65,138,139}. Seasonal sea-ice melt during summer also generates ice-free areas where air-sea gas exchange occurs, promoting CO₂ exchange¹⁴⁰. The mechanical effect of winds blowing over ice-free region can induce vertical mixing, which causes upwelling of deeper C-rich water and might trigger local CO₂ outgassing¹⁴¹. However, the same process might also trigger an injection of nutrients into the euphotic zone¹⁴², stimulating the biological C pump and promoting CO₂ uptake. Thus, climate-driven changes in lateral carbon and nutrient inputs, sea ice extent, and stratification as well as their impact on the biological carbon pump need to be quantified to estimate the Arctic Ocean carbon sink capacity in the future.

Estimates based on C-data products, ocean C cycle models, and atmospheric inversions quantify this Arctic Ocean sink to be -116 ± 4 Tg C yr⁻¹, -92 ± 30 Tg C yr⁻¹, and -91 ± 21 Tg C yr⁻¹, respectively¹⁴³ (omitting the full Nordic Seas, but including the seasonally sea-ice affected Greenland Sea). The overall sink capacity of the Arctic Ocean could decrease by over 10% by 2100 (ref.¹⁴⁴). However, CO₂ flux trends (1982-2020) for global coastal oceans show large spatial variability in the strength and direction of CO₂ fluxes in high latitude regions. Most regions show trends towards weaker sinks or stronger sources, but stronger sinks or weaker sources are observed in the Norwegian-Greenland Seas, Barents Sea, and parts of Baffin Bay and the Laptev Sea¹⁴⁵. The various Arctic Ocean shelf seas or sectors (Fig. 1) have different physical and

biogeochemical characteristics that locally control the seasonal dynamics of air-sea CO₂ fluxes¹²⁹. Thus, each sector needs to be considered when resolving the full Arctic Ocean basin air-sea CO₂ flux and any long-term changes.

The Barents Sea and the Chukchi Sea are inflow shelves and receive subpolar waters entering the Arctic Ocean from lower latitude oceans^{129,146}. These two Arctic Ocean sectors are the largest CO₂ sink owing to the influx of nutrients transported from lower latitudes promoting primary production and the size of the Barents Sea also means that air-sea CO₂ fluxes are integrated over a larger area. Based on available literature data, the sinks in these basins are estimated to be -21 and -77 Tg C yr⁻¹, respectively, with a computed mean value of -37 ± 15 Tg C yr⁻¹ (for further details see Supplementary Note 7 and Supplementary Table 6; Table 2; Fig. 4a). In the Chukchi Sea, CO₂ uptake ranges from -1 to -53 Tg C yr⁻¹, with a computed mean value of -11 ± 9 Tg C yr⁻¹ (Table 2; Fig. 4a), and the high CO₂ sink function being attributed to high levels of primary production fuelled by nutrients transported through the Bering Strait¹⁴⁷. Thus, inflow shelves are considered to be CO₂ sinks.

Interior shelves experience seasonal sea ice coverage and receive large volumes of river discharge, as such they are subject to strong land-ocean C cycle coupling. The wide Eurasian shelf (Kara, Laptev, and Eastern Siberian seas) and Beaufort Sea are interior shelves, with waters that mostly flow counterclockwise inside the Arctic Ocean. The Eurasian shelf is highly productive in summer¹⁴⁸, when seasonal sea ice melt occurs in combination with elevated Arctic river discharge and coastal erosion that supply nutrients (mainly nitrogen) of terrestrial origin^{65,78}. Erosion and river runoff are also responsible for large fluxes of OC that, when remineralized into inorganic C, can render some coastal portions of the Arctic Ocean sources of CO₂ (ref.^{15,79,149,150}). With estimated ranges of -1 to -16 Tg C yr⁻¹ for the Kara Sea, +0.9 to -12 Tg C yr⁻¹ for the Laptev Sea, and +2.7 to -8 Tg C yr⁻¹ for the Eastern Siberian Sea (Table 2; Fig. 4a), these areas provide a relatively small contribution to the total net CO₂ sink of the Arctic Ocean (sometimes even a net source) when compared to the Arctic Ocean inflow shelves. Mean computed values are -8.0 ± 4 , -3.1 ± 4 , and -1.8 ± 2.5 Tg C yr⁻¹ for the Kara, Laptev and East Siberian Sea, respectively. The Beaufort Sea is estimated to be a net CO₂ sink of +0.13 to -16 Tg C yr⁻¹ with a computed mean value of -1.3 ± 0.5 Tg C yr⁻¹ (Table 2; Fig. 4a), being much narrower than the Eurasian shelf seas and strongly influenced by seasonality in discharge from the Mackenzie River.

In outflow shelves, such as the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and Baffin Bay, Arctic waters exit southwards into the subpolar North Atlantic Ocean. These regions are considered a net CO₂ sink, with estimated ranges of -1.3 to -24 Tg C yr⁻¹ for the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, and -1.9 to -2.5 Tg C yr⁻¹ for Baffin Bay. Mean computed values of these areas are -11 ± 12.5 and -14 ± 6 Tg C yr⁻¹ for the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and Baffin Bay, respectively (Table 2; Fig. 4a). The Hudson Bay is another shallow inland sea that receives one third of all river discharge in Canada¹⁵¹ and is an outflow shelf but is often excluded from quantitative Arctic Ocean estimates. Estimates of the ice-free season CO₂ flux of Hudson Bay are scarce and uncertain¹⁵², but all point towards the bay varying between a weak sink (-0.58 ± 0.3 Tg)¹⁵³ and a weak source ($+1.6$ Tg)¹⁵⁴ (Table 2; Fig. 4a). Previous estimates have considered different portions of the Norwegian and Greenlandic Seas (Nordic Seas) to compute the full Arctic Ocean CO₂ sink. Considering this entire area with no distinction between the ice-covered season and ice-free-season, estimates are between -20.7 to -70 Tg C yr⁻¹, with a computed mean value of -42 ± 36 Tg C yr⁻¹ (Table 2; Fig. 4a). Outflow shelves, such as the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Baffin Bay, and parts of the Nordic Seas, act predominantly as net CO₂ sinks, although variability across regions and seasons underscores the need for refined flux estimates especially in the Hudson Bay and Nordic Seas.

The Bering Sea is a gateway connecting the North Pacific and Arctic Oceans via the Bering Strait. Seasonal sea-ice cover influences CO₂ uptake in this subpolar region that is thought to be a large CO₂ sink, with estimates biased towards spring and summer ranging from -122 to -192 Tg C yr⁻¹ (ref.¹⁵⁵). However, when

all four seasons are considered, CO₂ uptake in the Bering Sea is much less, ranging between -6.8 Tg C yr⁻¹ and -8.9 Tg C yr⁻¹, with a computed mean value of -7.8 ± 1.5 Tg C yr⁻¹ (Table 2; Fig. 4a).

Arctic fjord systems are not specifically discussed here but are worth mentioning owing to their high productivity¹⁵⁶ and disproportionately large role in terrestrial OC burial¹⁵⁷. Furthermore, even though the Arctic Ocean represents a net sink of CO₂, the drivers of marine emissions – including the scale of gas hydrate deposits in seafloor sediments, the size of the vulnerable C pool in submarine permafrost, the rate of emissions from seafloor sediments into the ocean, and the portion of CH₄ that could bypass the water column and reach the atmosphere – are poorly constrained^{5,115}. However, with increasing observational data, estimates of CH₄ emissions from shallow Arctic shelves, based on CH₄ concentrations in air and water, have increased in number, now ranging from 3 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ (ref.¹⁵⁸) to 17 Tg CH₄ yr⁻¹ (ref.¹⁵⁹).

Ocean-sediment fluxes

Shallow shelf seas comprise >50% of the Arctic Ocean¹¹ and are the primary recipients of remobilized terrestrial OC (terrOC). For example, evidence from the Laptev Sea continental margins suggests that over 80% of the total terrOC exported to the Arctic Ocean is either accumulated or re-mineralized within the continental shelf system¹⁶⁰. For consistency, accumulation rates are reported here as negative fluxes as they represent a sink in the integrated Arctic system.

Mass accumulation rates of OC (OC-MAR) can be estimated from the analysis of sedimentation rates and dry bulk density in combination with OC concentrations of sediment cores. Millennial-scale OC-MAR in circum-Arctic shelf sediments has been estimated at -8.7 Tg C yr⁻¹ with -5.5 Tg C yr⁻¹ being of terrestrial origin based on $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of OC and terrestrial biomarkers³¹ (Supplementary Note 8, Supplementary Table 7). Another estimate more accurately resolved MAR rates over the past 1-2 centuries and discriminated marine and terrigenous OC (terrOC) components, producing a more detailed and generally higher OC-MAR (-34 Tg C yr⁻¹ alone for the Laptev and East Siberian seas)¹⁶¹ when compared to the millennial-scale assessments. The latest and most comprehensive estimate of OC-MAR suggests a total of -94 ± 44 Tg C yr⁻¹ across the Arctic Ocean shelf seas, of which -45 ± 18 Tg C yr⁻¹ is thought to be of terrestrial origin (Fig. 3b, Supplementary Table 1)⁹³.

To account for sediment resuspension, the seafloor can be categorised as net depositional seafloor (>30 m water depth, 74% of the circum-Arctic shelf area) and near-coastal areas affected by wind and wave-related re-suspension (<30 m, 26% of the shelf area)^{160,161}, building on observations from the East Siberian Sea¹⁶². Based on this inferred distinction, the cumulative OC-MAR on the net depositional seafloor region is -66 ± 23 Tg yr⁻¹, with the largest OC accumulation rates found in the Barents, Kara, and East Siberian shelf seas, followed by the Chukchi Sea and the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, and the Laptev and Beaufort shelf seas (Table 2). Together with the dynamic shallow shelf and near-coastal areas (<30 m), the OC-MAR in the circum-Arctic is -112 ± 41 Tg yr⁻¹ (Table 2).

The relative contribution of terrOC and marine OC to OC-MAR varies across the Arctic shelf. Dual-carbon isotope source apportionment ($\delta^{13}\text{C} / \Delta^{14}\text{C}$) suggests that the total terrOC MAR of circum-Arctic shelf sediment is -61 ± 26 Tg C yr⁻¹, and marine OC MAR accounts for -42 ± 21 Tg C yr⁻¹ (ref.⁹³). The largest terrOC MARs are found in the Kara (-15.3 ± 6.9 Tg C yr⁻¹), East Siberian (-18.3 ± 6.0 Tg C yr⁻¹), and Laptev seas (-15.7 ± 4.9 Tg C yr⁻¹). By contrast, marine OC dominates OC-MAR stocks in the Barents (-8.2 ± 5.4) and Chukchi Seas (-6.4 ± 1.7 Tg C yr⁻¹), as well as in the Canadian Arctic Archipelago (-3.8 ± 2.5 Tg C yr⁻¹). However, large uncertainties remain due to spatial variability of OC-MAR, poorly constrained sediment transport, resuspension, and re-mineralization processes, as well as limitations in constraining isotopic end members, with partly overlapping source compartments.

OC transport and degradation processes contribute to large uncertainties, limiting comparisons with fluxes in other sub-systems of the Arctic C cycle. TerrOC becomes increasingly degraded with distance

offshore^{163,164} and transport time¹⁶⁵ along the Siberian shelf. A quantitative budget of terrOC input and output in the Laptev Sea continental margin suggests that 56% of terrOC is removed via water column re-mineralization, with 44% accumulating in sediments^{68,160,166}. Further re-mineralization following deposition releases dissolved CO₂ and, to a smaller degree, CH₄ back to the water column, with the available observational evidence suggesting that as much as half of the terrOC accumulated on the Arctic shelf and slope sediments is potentially re-mineralized¹⁶⁰. Nonetheless, the circum-Arctic pattern of terrOC receptor fluxes broadly resembles the distribution pattern of its sources on land, permitting estimates of integrated terrOC release by comparing terrOC accumulation in shelf sediments relative to land-based terrOC stocks. One such estimate has shown stronger relative terrOC transport in drainage basins most affected by Arctic warming (East Siberian Sea, Canadian Arctic Archipelago), with the analysis also being sensitive to terrOC degradation during long-distance transport⁹³.

The Arctic Ocean including its sediments functions as a strong net carbon sink, whereas the northern circumpolar drainage basin serves as a weak net carbon sink, characterized by substantial uncertainties and discrepancies between top-down and bottom-up estimates. Emissions from disturbances and inland waters reduce the overall terrestrial carbon sink.

Summary and future perspectives

The integrated Arctic system (terrestrial and marine combined) is presently an overall C sink (Fig. 5), largely driven by oceanic uptake of CO₂ (-127 ± 36 Tg C yr⁻¹) from the atmosphere and OC accumulation into shelf sediments (-112 ± 41 Tg C yr⁻¹). The marine sink is countered with terrestrial emissions of CH₄ (38 (21, 53) Tg yr⁻¹) and a weak but highly uncertain terrestrial source of CO₂ (12 (-606, 661) Tg C yr⁻¹) (Table 2). The magnitude of this overall sink (terrestrial and marine combined) is expected to weaken. Ocean warming and changes in deep water formation might reduce ocean CO₂ uptake¹⁶⁷. Conversely, reduced sea ice cover increases the CO₂ sink potential, and shifts the seasonality of air-sea flux with an expected increase in CO₂ uptake during fall. Increased coastal erosion inputs of OC will reduce oceanic CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere by 4.6-13.2 Tg C yr⁻¹ by 2100 (ref.¹⁵⁰), and river OC discharge could turn nearshore areas into CO₂ sources through outgassing^{15,79}. The OC sink function of the Arctic shelf sediments is also expected to become smaller, with more physical and biological activity amplifying nearshore OC turnover. Terrestrial ecosystems are still a weak net CO₂ sink, and CO₂ uptake by plants could increase with warming and greater biomass production, known as Arctic greening^{168,169}. However, this uptake is substantially offset by increasing soil respiration¹⁷⁰, ground disturbances such as fire and thermokarst³⁹, and inland water emissions¹⁷¹. For freshwater bodies in northern terrestrial ecosystems, the net CO₂ fluxes per area are typically much greater than of the surrounding land^{126,172} and this active pipe function¹²⁶, reflected in increasing DIC fluxes, and DOC processing, is expected to strengthen.

The increasing number of Arctic observations and continuous model developments have led to a better mechanistic understanding of the Arctic C cycle and changes that lie ahead. However, Earth System Models could benefit further from incorporation of Arctic-specific processes⁶³. Within such frameworks, uniform and consistent boundaries for Arctic system definitions should be used. For example, instead of divisions based on latitude, biome, or climatic regime, boundaries based on hydrological principles that use watersheds and recipient shelf sea basins (Fig. 1a) would better represent the integrated Arctic system. Similarly, transnational collaboration and coordinated research activities across Arctic countries should aim to overcome geopolitical barriers and ensure appropriate representation of all sectors in the Arctic system. Applying a combination of remote sensing, modelling, geoinformatics, and sample archives could help avoid such biases in observations and data coverage.

Mechanistic understanding of processes and regional response dynamics of Arctic systems (Fig. 5) will ensure correct model parameterization, and accurate projections of responses to ongoing environmental change. For example, fjords likely have an important role in the Arctic C cycle, serving as hotspots for OC

burial¹⁷³ with about 18 Tg yr⁻¹ of OC buried in fjord sediments globally¹⁵⁷. However, the fate (mineralization versus burial¹⁷⁴) of C in Arctic fjords is poorly constrained. In addition, the observed reduction in CO₂ uptake in the Canada Basin of the Arctic Ocean owing to ocean warming and increased stratification, in comparison to enhanced CO₂ uptake under the same ocean warming in the Chukchi Sea¹⁷⁵ further highlight the need to constrain regional differences. Maximising the potential of satellite observations (for example the high-resolution data from Copernicus Sentinel 2) and state-of-the-art sensors, for example for CDOM on marine moorings, can help detect and quantify rapid changes in the Arctic C cycle, both regionally and as an integrated system.

Improved observational coverage and characterization of landscape parameters are also needed to support bottom-up scaling and detect change across heterogeneous Arctic landscapes (Fig. 5, Box 1). In terrestrial systems, more data on ground ice and SOC distributions, and better validation of diffusive flux gas transfer coefficients are needed¹⁷⁶, particularly for Russia, Scandinavia, Greenland, and Eastern Canada¹¹⁸, and in dry tundra systems and boreal forests²⁷. Certain geomorphological domains are also underrepresented, including small catchments (smaller than 100 km²), permafrost lowlands with deep ice-rich soils prone to thermokarst^{7,34}, and higher elevation areas¹⁷⁷. In marine systems, improved data coverage of the nearshore zones in general and the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Russian Arctic shelf seas, Hudson and Baffin bays and accurate assessments of OC lability and quantification of the role of iron in stabilizing OC during burial are needed¹⁷⁸. Areas experiencing rapid change and areas that are representative of large sections of the Arctic, such as ice-wedge polygon terrain, should be a focus of future research to avoid potential bias, for example towards rapidly eroding hotspots or singular thermokarst landforms.

Similarly, better understanding of Arctic tipping points¹⁷⁹, climate feedbacks and their links with C sink-to-source transitions¹⁸⁰ are needed, including the influence of extreme events, large-scale disturbances, and non-linear responses. The timing and magnitude of these processes is difficult to assess, thus they are often omitted in climate projections. For example, no ESMs account for nonlinear processes such as wildfire and thermokarst^{39,181}, despite their prevalence. Thus, the short- and long-term impacts of non-linear events such as wildfire, heatwaves, and thermokarst on local and regional C cycling are a clear priority. Advanced proxies and tracers, including inorganic isotopes such as silicon, as well as the use of large-scale geospatial data platforms, can help provide insight into such impacts on soil-water exchange and the timing and degree of connectivity across landscapes¹⁸². Future research should therefore cross system boundaries (land-ocean-atmosphere), time periods (historical and present day) and spatial scales to increase mechanistic understanding of processes, non-linear change, extremes, and feedback mechanisms with holistic and transdisciplinary approaches, such as the long-term [Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring](#)¹⁸³. In parallel, scientific complexity needs to be conveyed and communicated to the general public and policy makers, to avoid the perception of uncertainty and unknowns, and instead emphasize the agreement on mechanistic insights.

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Author contributions

JEV and MF designed the study, led the writing and contributed equally. NJS designed most of the figures. All authors contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Related links

- **Arctic Great Rivers Observatory (ArcticGRO):** <https://arcticgreatrivers.org/>
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- **Copernicus Arctic Ocean Physics re-analysis:** <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00007>
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- **Northern Circumpolar Soil Carbon Database (NCSCD):** <https://bolin.su.se/data/ncscd/>
- **REgional Carbon Cycle Assessment and Processes (RECCAP2):** <https://www.globalcarbonproject.org/reccap/>
- **The pan-ARctic CAtachment DatabasE (ARCADE):** <https://dataverse.nl/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.34894/U9HSPV>

Data availability

The data and data sources for Figures 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 are provided in Tables 1 and 2. Further data sources are provided in the captions. Shapefiles of terrestrial catchments and ocean basins used in this review are available under: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12166101>.

Supplementary information

Supplementary information is available for this paper at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-024-00627-w>.

Tables

Table 1 | Carbon stocks across the integrated Arctic system.

Parameter	Land-ocean regions (drainage basin and corresponding shelf sea)											TOTAL
	Barents Sea	Kara Sea	Laptev Sea	East Siberian Sea	Chukchi Sea	Bering Sea	Beaufort Sea	Canadian Arctic Archipelago	Hudson Bay	Baffin Bay	Greenland & Norwegian Sea	
Drainage area (10 ³ km ²)	1365	7069	3622	1323	255	1070	2104	1735	3965	971	772	24251
Shelf sea area (10 ³ km ²)	1790	941	504	999	645	1177	184	1169	1385	656	657	10107
Shelf sea volume (10 ³ km ³)	360	123	22.9	57.7	55.4	82.4*	25.8	259	157	206	164	1513
Terrestrial sediments (Pg C, mean ± s.d.)												
Active layer (0-300cm) ¹⁸⁴	3.18 ± 0.15	32.1 ± 1.5	46.4 ± 2.2	17.3 ± 0.8	3.29 ± 0.15	9.65 ± 0.45	13.8 ± 0.6	18.5 ± 0.9	25.9 ± 1.2	2.72 ± 0.13	0.753 ± 0.035	174 ± 3
Permafrost (0-300cm) ¹⁸⁴	24.5 ± 1.1	156 ± 7	95.6 ± 4.4	41.5 ± 1.9	9.84 ± 0.45	31.3 ± 1.5	43.8 ± 1.9	44.8 ± 2.0	77.8 ± 3.7	9.51 ± 0.44	5.17 ± 0.24	540 ± 10
Non-permafrost terrain (0-200cm) ¹⁸⁵	30.4 ± 1.4	138 ± 6	7.63 ± 0.35	1.17 ± 0.05	0.265 ± 0.013	10.7 ± 0.5	24.9 ± 1.2	3.37 ± 0.16	66.9 ± 3.0	2.11 ± 0.10	7.14 ± 0.33	292 ± 7
Upper permafrost (0-30cm)	0.457 ± 0.021	3.70 ± 0.17	3.15 ± 0.15	1.85 ± 0.09	0.427 ± 0.020	1.01 ± 0.05	2.13 ± 0.10	3.69 ± 0.17	3.64 ± 0.17	0.316 ± 0.015	0.126 ± 0.006	20.5 ± 0.4
Total drainage region (nonPF 0-200 cm, PF 0-300 cm)	45.8 ± 2.1	265 ± 12	147 ± 7	59.9 ± 2.8	13.4 ± 0.6	43.7 ± 2.0	69.1 ± 3.2	66.4 ± 3.1	142 ± 6	13.8 ± 0.6	11.9 ± 0.54	877 ± 16
Marine sediments (Tg C for 0-1cm, Pg for 0-100cm, mean ± s.d.)												
Surface (0-1 cm)	170 ± 43	85 ± 14	49 ± 11	83 ± 13	51 ± 9	-	17 ± 4	74 ± 13	-	-	-	529 ± 107
Upper meter (0-100 cm)	29.6 ± 12.7	11.2 ± 5.2	7.5 ± 1.6	10.2 ± 5.6	10.0 ± 2.4	-	3.0 ± 1.5	10.8 ± 5.7	-	-	-	82.3 ± 34.8
Marine water column (Tg C) mean ± s.d. or mean (min – max)												
DOC (salinity-derived)	224 ± 3.2 ^a	103 ± 6.7 ^a	31.6 ± 4.4 ^a	76.4 ± 9.8 ^b	49.4 ± 4.7 ^c	-	21.7 ± 1.9 ^b	-	-	-	-	506 ± 14.0
Labile DOC (modelled)	44.4 ± 0.14	16.6 ± 0.11	3.1 ± 0.02	8.0 ± 0.21	6.6 ± 0.1	13.7 ± 0.13	2.2 ± 0.07	25.6 ± 0.25	20.6 ± 0.14	20.7 ± 0.11	17.5 ± 0.09	172 ± 0.38
Annual NPP (modelled)	106 ± 5.3	48.3 ± 1.8	37.6 ± 5.7	49.3 ± 9.2	52.8 ± 4.8	170 ± 8.3	9.9 ± 1.8	24.1 ± 1.7	119.5 ± 5.3	37.5 ± 1.0	35.4 ± 2.0	691 ± 18.0
Annual NPP (remote sensing)	61.0 (34.8 – 106.8)	22.9 (13.1 – 40.1)	19.6 (11.2 – 34.3)	15.3 (8.7 – 26.8)	9.1 (5.2 – 15.9)	50.7 (29 – 88.8)	4.9 (2.8 – 8.6)	5.5 (3.1 – 9.6)	24.1 (13.8 – 42.2)	12.6 (7.2 – 22.1)	15.0 (8.6 – 26.3)	241 (137.7 – 421.9)

Drainage basin and shelf sea areas according to shapefiles provided at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12166101>. Barents Sea includes the White Sea. * Calculated based on shelf area assuming a mean depth of 70m. PF, permafrost; DOC, dissolved organic carbon; NPP, net primary production. ^aHigh confidence. ^bMedium confidence. ^cLow confidence.

Table 2 | Carbon fluxes across the integrated Arctic system.

Parameter	Land-ocean regions (drainage basin and corresponding shelf sea)											TOTAL
	Barents Sea	Kara Sea	Laptev Sea	East Siberian Sea	Chukchi Sea	Bering Sea	Beaufort Sea	Canadian Arctic Archipelago	Hudson Bay	Baffin Bay	Greenland & Norwegian Sea	
Drainage area (10 ³ km ²)	1365	7069	3622	1323	255	1070	2104	1735	3965	971	772	24251
Shelf sea area (10 ³ km ²)	1790	941	504	999	645	1177	184	1169	1385	656	657	10107
Shelf sea volume (10 ³ km ³)	360	123	22.9	57.7	55.4	82.4*	25.8	259	157	206	164	1513
Fluvial (Tg C yr ⁻¹ mean with credible min – max)												
DOC	3.65 (1.8-6.6)	11.4 (10-19)	7.78 (1.8-9.0)	1.70 (0.96-2.0)	0.39 (0.031-1.5)	1.69 (0.13-6.3)	2.10 (0.84-4.2)	2.45 (0.21-10)	5.88 (0.50-25)	0.96 (0.20-1.2)	1.52 (0.12-5.8)	39.5 (17-90)
POC	0.56 (0.0027-3.6)	1.43 (0.64-1.3)	0.87 (0.18-0.91)	0.48 (0.32-0.67)	0.10 (0.00052-0.69)	0.67 (0.00021-2.8)	0.92 (0.39-5.5)	0.69 (0.0035-4.6)	1.67 (0.0084-11)	0.43 (0.0022-2.9)	0.39 (0.0020-2.6)	8.21 (1.5-37)
DIC	4.06 (0.67-7.3)	17.0 (14-21)	8.80 (1.8-11)	2.28 (1.4-2.0)	0.65 (0.13-1.4)	5.06 (0.52-5.7)	7.34 (1.0-11)	4.37 (0.85-9.3)	10.6 (2.1-23)	2.74 (0.53-5.9)	2.51 (0.49-5.3)	65.4 (23-102)
Erosion (Tg C yr ⁻¹ with RMSE)												
ACD based range ¹⁰⁵	0.8	0.35-1.0	0.66-3.7	2.2-7.3	0.8	-	0.21-0.37	-	-	-	-	4.9-14
Total annual SOC transfer (erosion > 1m yr ⁻¹)	0.40 ^c	0.25 ^c	0.19 ^c	0.58 ^c	0.06 ^c	0.12 ^c	0.31 ^c	0.32 ^c	-	0.05 ^c	0.02 ^c	2.74 ^c
Total annual SOC transfer (erosion > 2m yr ⁻¹) with RMSE	0.30 (0.047) ^b	0.19 (0.021) ^b	0.13 (0.018) ^b	0.51 (0.054) ^b	0.03 (0.008) ^b	0.15 (0.020) ^b	0.24 (0.030) ^b	0.28 (0.028) ^b	-	0.05 (0.006) ^b	0.02 (0.004) ^b	2.03 (0.25) ^b
Terrestrial land – atmosphere (Tg C yr ⁻¹ , top-down mean ± s.d., bottom-up mean and 95% CI)												
Top-down CO ₂ **	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-740 ± 220
Bottom-up CO ₂ *** (RECCAP2 ³¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12 (-606, 661)
Bottom-up CH ₄ *** (RECCAP2 ³¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	38 (21, 53)
Bottom-up CO ₂ **** (RECCAP2 ²⁷)	-16.1 (-48, 6.4)	-68.9 (-204, 21.1)	-51.0 (-180, 27.3)	-9.84 (-49, 20.1)	-0.46 (-7.8, 5.4)	-9.96 (-42, 13.7)	-21.2 (-70, 13.8)	-0.029 (-27.6, 27.3)	-38.8 (-110, 13.6)	-0.05 (-5.1, 4.9)	-1.21 (-5.8, 2.5)	-218 (-749, 156)
Bottom-up CH ₄ **** (RECCAP2)	2.04 (1.2, 2.8)	8.1 (4.8, 11.3)	0.72 (-0.4, 1.8)	0.75 (0.23, 1.23)	0.21 (0.07, 0.33)	0.76 (0.25, 1.23)	2.82 (1.61, 3.98)	0.72 (0.22, 1.17)	6.57 (4.14, 8.9)	0.11 (0.02, 0.19)	0.121 (0.04, 0.2)	22.9 (12.2, 33.2)
Terrestrial inland aquatic – atmosphere (Tg C yr ⁻¹) (mean and 95% CI) †												
Lake CH ₄	0.24 (0.11, 0.3)	1.9 (1, 2.3)	0.5 (0.2, 0.7)	0.5 (0.2, 0.7)	0.072 (0.03, 0.1)	0.3 (0.12, 0.4)	1 (0.1, 4)	0.6 (0.2, 1.0)	2 (0.8, 3.2)	0.072 (0.02, 0.13)	0.02 (0.001, 0.04)	7.21 (2.8, 12.9)
Lake CO ₂	1.87 (0.71, 3.0)	10.6 (4, 17)	3.1 (1.2, 5)	3.06 (1.2, 5)	0.39 (0.15, 0.64)	1.68 (0.63, 2.72)	12.6 (4.8, 20.5)	7.95 (3, 12.9)	27 (10.2, 43.8)	1.06 (0.4, 1.7)	0.44 (0.17, 0.72)	69.7 (26.4, 113)
River CH ₄	0.1 (0.07, 0.14)	0.6 (0.4, 0.7)	0.6 (0.4, 0.7)	0.15 (0.11, 0.2)	0.019 (0.01, 0.025)	0.2 (0.13, 0.27)	0.2 (0.13, 0.25)	0.06 (0.04, 0.074)	0.2 (0.13, 0.24)	0.017 (0.01, 0.02)	0.015 (0.01, 0.019)	2.2 (1.4, 2.8)
River CO ₂	9.23 (6.7, 15.5)	49.9 (32.4, 84.5)	50.7 (32.9, 68.4)	13.7 (8.9, 18.5)	1.71 (1.11, 2.3)	16.5 (10.8, 22.3)	17.2 (11.2, 23.3)	5.05 (2.2, 6.8)	16.7 (10.9, 22.5)	1.5 (1, 2)	1.3 (0.85, 2.5)	184 (119, 248)

Total CH ₄ , CO ₂	0.34, 11	2.5, 60	1.1, 54	0.65, 16.8	0.091, 2.1	0.5, 18	1.2, 30	0.66, 13	2.2, 44	0.089, 2.56	0.17, 1.7	9.41, 253
Ocean – atmosphere (Tg C yr ⁻¹ , mean ± s.d.)												
CO ₂	-37.2 ± 15	-8.0 ± 4	-3.1 ± 4	-1.8 ± 2.5	-11 ± 9	-7.8 ± 1.5	-1.3 ± 0.5	-11 ± 12.5	-0.58 to +1.6	-14 ± 6.0	-42 ± 36	-127 ± 36
Ocean – sediment (Tg C yr ⁻¹ , mean ± s.d.)												
Terrestrial OC (<30m)	-0.2 ± 0.1	-7.1 ± 3.4	-11.9 ± 3.4	-11.0 ± 4.0	-0.1 ± 0.1	-	-2.3 ± 2.2	-0.2 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-33 ± 13
Marine OC (<30m)	-0.2 ± 0.2	-4.5 ± 2.4	-3.3 ± 1.1	-2.0 ± 1.1	-0.1 ± 0.1	-	-0.5 ± 0.5	-0.3 ± 0.2	-	-	-	-11 ± 6
Total OC (<30m)	-0.5 ± 0.4	-11.6 ± 5.0	-15.2 ± 4.3	-13.0 ± 4.6	-0.2 ± 0.1	-	-4.4 ± 3.6	-0.8 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-46 ± 18
Terrestrial OC (>30m)	-4.3 ± 3.0	-8.2 ± 3.6	-3.8 ± 1.5	-7.3 ± 2.0	-2.6 ± 0.7	-	-0.7 ± 0.4	-1.8 ± 1.0	-	-	-	-29 ± 12
Marine OC (>30m)	-8.0 ± 5.2	-6.0 ± 2.8	-2.5 ± 1.0	-4.8 ± 1.7	-6.2 ± 1.6	-	-0.5 ± 0.3	-3.4 ± 2.3	-	-	-	-31 ± 15
Total OC (>30m)	-14.6 ± 8.5	-14.2 ± 5.6	-6.3 ± 2.3	-12.1 ± 2.1	-8.8 ± 2.3	-	-1.7 ± 0.4	-8.3 ± 2.1	-	-	-	-66 ± 23
Terrestrial OC (full shelf)	-4.5 ± 3.2	-15.3 ± 6.9	-15.7 ± 4.9	-18.3 ± 6.0	-2.7 ± 0.8	-	-3.0 ± 2.6	-2.0 ± 1.1	-	-	-	-61 ± 26
Marine OC (full shelf)	-8.2 ± 5.4	-10.5 ± 5.2	-5.8 ± 2.2	-6.8 ± 2.9	-6.4 ± 1.7	-	-1.0 ± 0.7	-3.8 ± 2.5	-	-	-	-42 ± 21
Total OC (full shelf)	-15.1 ± 8.9	-25.9 ± 10.5	-21.5 ± 6.6	-25.1 ± 6.7	-9.1 ± 2.4	-	-6.1 ± 4.0	-9.1 ± 2.2	-	-	-	-112 ± 41

Drainage basin and shelf sea areas according to shapefiles provided in the Supplementary Notes with Ocean-Atmosphere Hudson Bay data from ^{172,173}. Barents Sea includes the White Sea. * Calculated based on shelf area assuming a mean depth of 70m; ** Including emissions from inland waters; *** Terrestrial emissions including disturbance (fire, abrupt thaw) and including inland waters; **** Terrestrial emissions excluding disturbance and inland waters; † only from inland waters; ACD, Arctic Coastal Dynamics database; SOC, soil organic carbon; OC, organic carbon. RMSE, root mean squared error; ^b medium confidence, ^c low confidence.

Figures

Fig. 1 | The integrated Arctic system. a. | Topography, bathymetry, permafrost and sea ice extent, and the major river basins in the Arctic system. Dotted black lines indicate the main regions and their respective drainage basins²⁶ (10³ km²), freshwater discharge¹⁸⁶ (km³ yr⁻¹) and shelf area (10³ km²) (note: Hudson Bay refers collectively to Hudson Bay, Hudson Strait, Fox Basin). **b.** | Temperature anomaly north of 66.5°N (°C, 1979–2023) relative to the ERA5 1981–2010 reference period. Red bars indicate warmer years than the reference period; blue bars indicate cooler years. Data from [Copernicus Climate Change Service \(C3S/ECMWF\)](#). **c.** | Sea ice extent during September (10⁶ km², 1979–2023). Dashed line represents the linear regression. Data from [Meereisportal](#). The northern circumpolar drainage basin has close hydrological connectivity with its recipient shelf basins and this integrated Arctic system is exposed to anthropogenic climate warming.

a Soil organic carbon

b Hydrologically accessible soil organic carbon

c Coastal erosion organic carbon fluxes

d Fluvial carbon yields and fluxes

Fig. 2 | Soil carbon stocks and release pathways. a. | Soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks (kg C m⁻² in the upper 0-300cm, shading). Inset bar graphs show the contribution of active layer (pale teal) and permafrost (mid-teal) soils to the total (dark teal)^{184,185} over the surface 0-300 cm. **b.** | Total hydrologically-accessible SOC stock (SOC_{HA}, kg C m⁻²) in the active layer, and upper 30cm of permafrost and non-permafrost soils combined (shading). Inset pie charts show the distribution of SOC stocks between waterlogged (white), ecotone (light green), hillslope (mid green) and

plateau (dark green) terrain classes, indicative of Height Above Nearest Drainage (HAND⁴³, %). **c.** | Coastal erosion SOC fluxes¹⁰⁹ (10^6 kg C yr⁻¹, discrete coloured datapoints). Inset bar graphs show other organic carbon erosion fluxes (Tg C yr⁻¹) per region at different erosion rates based on the Arctic Coastal Dynamics database (ACD-based, light orange), >1 m yr⁻¹ (orange), >2 m yr⁻¹ (dark orange). No data are available for Hudson Bay. Upper estimates are provided in brackets, if available. **d.** | Catchment-specific DOC yield (g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, shading) (Supplementary Table 5). Inset bar graphs show dissolved organic carbon (DOC, light brown), particulate organic carbon (mid brown), and dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC, dark brown) flux per drainage basin (Tg C yr⁻¹). Data, uncertainties data sources are provided in Table 1 and Table 2. There is large regional variability in soil OC stocks, some of which are hydrologically accessible and can be released via coastal erosion and fluvial transport.

a Sedimentary organic carbon

b Organic carbon mass accumulation rates

c Water column dissolved organic carbon

d Water column primary production

Fig. 3 | Marine organic carbon stocks and accumulation rates. a. | Spatially-resolved surface sediment organic carbon content (OC SED, wt%, shading)²⁵. Inset bar graphs show total sediment organic carbon stocks for the surface 0-1 cm (Tg, light brown) and 0-100 cm (Pg, dark brown) sediments in each marine basin. **b.** | Accumulation of terrestrial organic carbon as mass accumulation rate (OC MAR, g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, shading)⁹³. Inset bar graphs show total (terrestrial and marine) OC accumulation (Tg C yr⁻¹) for regions with <30 m water depth (light purple), >30 m water depth (mid purple) and the total shelf (dark purple). **c.** | Mean absorption of detrital and dissolved organic carbon

(Mean DOC Abs., m^{-1} , shading)¹⁸⁷. Inset bar graphs show total DOC stocks per marine basin (Tg) estimated using NEMO-PISCES model output (yellow) and remote sensing (mustard yellow). **d.** | Annual net primary production (NPP, $g\ C\ m^{-2}\ yr^{-1}$, shading)¹⁸⁸. Inset bar graphs show total NPP stocks per marine basin (Tg) estimated using models (pale green) and remote sensing (green). All data, uncertainties and data sources are provided in Table 1 and Table 2; no data are available for Hudson Bay, if available upper estimates are provided in brackets. Stocks of marine sediment and water column OC are regionally variable but generally show higher values in coastal areas.

Fig. 4 | Vertical carbon fluxes across the integrated Arctic system. a. | Top-down estimates of annual terrestrial CO₂ fluxes ($g\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$, shaded map). **b.** | Bottom-up estimates of total annual vertical fluxes ($Tg\ C\ yr^{-1}$) of air-sea CO₂, terrestrial CO₂* and CH₄* (*excluding emissions from disturbance and inland aquatic systems), and inland aquatic emissions of CO₂ and CH₄. Positive values indicate net emission (source); negative values indicate net uptake (sink). All data and their uncertainties can be found in Table 2. **c.** | The proportion of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes from lakes and

rivers for the terrestrial drainage basins derived from ref.²⁷, with summed fluxes (CO₂ + CH₄ in Tg C) and summed fluxes normalized for drainage area (Tg C per 10⁶ km²). All sector-specific data is in Table 2. Although the Arctic Ocean is a strong net C sink, the northern circumpolar drainage basin is a weak net C sink with large uncertainties and variable top-down and bottom-up estimates. Emissions from disturbances and from inland waters lower the terrestrial carbon sink.

Fig. 5 | Carbon cycling across the integrated Arctic system. Carbon stocks (Pg, blue boxes), processes impacting carbon stocks (white boxes), and lateral and vertical carbon fluxes (Tg C yr⁻¹, blue boxes with arrows) across different components of the Arctic system. CO₂, carbon dioxide; CH₄, methane; DOC, dissolved organic carbon; POC, particulate organic carbon; DIC, dissolved organic carbon; OC, organic carbon; SOC, soil organic carbon; NPP, net primary production. Adapted from ²³, Springer Nature Limited. Stocks and fluxes of OC across the integrated Arctic system still come with large uncertainties. To reduce uncertainties, it is necessary to increase mechanistic understanding of processes, non-linear change, extremes, and feedback mechanisms.

Box 1: Uncertainties and research priorities

Priorities to address uncertainties in the major stocks and fluxes in the integrated Arctic system are summarized.

Terrestrial stocks

- Uncertainties: C stocks in soils >3m, quantity and distribution of ground ice and permafrost peatlands.
- Priorities: mapping ground ice, peatlands and wetlands at pan-Arctic scales, and including OC content and ground ice in the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P).

Marine water column stocks

- Uncertainties: NPP, POC and DOC stocks during spring and winter and poor observational coverage (particularly in the Eurasian sector).
- Priorities: extending the use of autonomous observing platforms and improving representation of lateral fluxes and sediment dynamics in (Arctic Ocean) numerical simulations.

Marine sediment stocks

- Uncertainties: inorganic C stocks, sediment thickness distributions, and OC source apportionment.
- Priorities: mapping and modelling Holocene shelf sea sediment cover, and using CASCADE as a coherent repository of tracer and biomarker data.

Fluvial lateral flux

- Uncertainties: the seasonality of fluxes and underrepresentation of small and fringing basins.
- Priorities: prioritizing observations based on representative landscape units, establishing long-term observatories within smaller catchments, and applying (isotopic) tracers across scales.

Erosion lateral flux

- Uncertainties: insufficient terrestrial OC data to support upscaling, coarse spatial resolution of satellite acquisitions, and defining coastline positions.
- Priorities: increasing SOC measurements along coastlines, creating a pan-Arctic erosion time series datasets, and using high-resolution satellite observations.

Land-atmosphere fluxes

- Uncertainties: the susceptibility of permafrost C to microbial degradation, and data limitation of inverse model systems.
- Priorities: improving data coverage in bottom-up scaling, analysing prior flux data influence on final posterior flux estimates in inversion systems, and constraining non-linear ecosystem changes.

Inland aquatic system-atmosphere flux

- Uncertainties: ebullitive and ice-out fluxes, small water body contributions, CO₂ sequestration in aquatic ecosystems.
- Priorities: representation of aquatic vertical CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes in top-down models, synthesizing available lake C flux data, and measuring ebullitive and ice-out fluxes.

Ocean-atmosphere flux

- Uncertainties: poor spatiotemporal resolution C data, especially in the Eurasian sector, and poor understanding and model representation of gas exchange through sea ice.
- Priorities: determining the biological C pump response to plankton community shifts, the response of marine bacteria to lateral carbon and nutrient fluxes, and quantifying competing effects on CO₂ exchange (i.e., wind, stratification, sea ice, open water).

Ocean-sediment flux

- Uncertainties: OC mineralization rates and OC lability, spatial variability in sedimentation rates and OC MAR, and poorly constrained sediment transport and resuspension.
- Priorities: extending spatial coverage of Pb/Cs chronologies and OC MAR, particularly in nearshore zones, and conducting OC degradation and mineralization experiments.